

Cosmos Evolution Based on Transition Theory

John G. Vlachogiannis

R.S. Lianokladiou, 35100, Lamia, Greece
vlachogiannis@gmail.com

Abstract

The evolutionary phases of Cosmos based on the cosmological model of Transition Theory (TT) are represented. The dark matter-energy is calculated based on the concept of TT that the infinite dimensional space absorbs matter-energy while hidden space-dimensions are brought out. Promised results compared to experimental ones are obtained.

Keywords: Cosmology, Transition theory, Infinite-dimensional space, Dark matter, Dark energy, Logarithmic spiral, Fibonacci sequence.

1 Introduction

In the past centuries, there has been increasing interest and research works on Cosmology, more specifically in the fields of Big Bang and Cosmos evolution. This paper presents the evolutionary phases of Cosmos based on recently introduced Transition Theory (TT) [1]. The TT was inspired by the following text of Plato's Cave: (*"Republic" VII, 514a-516b*): *"People in the cave (our Cosmos) spend their time playing games and identifying the shadows on the wall. They think that the shadows on the wall (physical observations) are the real things. They (scientists) are happy to win prizes in the cave for being so quick and accurate at identifying the shadows. They do not know that those are just shadows (physical observations in the 3-D space) caused by the light of fire (speed-of-light: $c=299792458$ m/sec) crossing over the statues which are themselves representations of the things outside the cave (Cosmos with more space-dimensions) and all of those would not exist if not for the source of all things and all life, the sun (Light with higher speed than $c=299792458$ m/sec)."*

The TT introduced the concept that Cosmos is absorbed by infinite-dimensional space while more space-dimensions are revealed. Also, in accordance of TT, the time exists due to the existence of hidden space-dimensions [1].

2 Basic on Transition Theory

Cosmos is composed of energy of matter and energy of fields (organized matter-energy) and energy of space (non-organized space-energy). The transformation of organized matter-energy to non-organized space-energy is represented in accordance with the TT [2]. This transformation occurs due to the fact of representation of matter-energy into space with infinite dimensions and higher speeds of light [1]. Namely, an endless-dimensional space absorbs the matter-energy of Cosmos while more space-dimensions are brought out [2].

Based on TT, if there are continuous evolutionary phases of Cosmos, these will take place in accordance of Fibonacci sequence as [1]:

$$(1, U_1, 0) \rightarrow (2, U_2, 1) \rightarrow (2, U_{2A}, 1) \rightarrow (3, U_3, 2) \rightarrow (4, U_4=c, 3) \rightarrow \dots (F_j+1, U_{F_j+1}, j) \quad (1)$$

where: F_j is the number of j -th term of Fibonacci sequence which is equal to number of space dimensions and U_{F_j+1} is the speed of light of (F_j+1) -dimensional space-time.

The transformation of organized matter-energy of (F_m+1) -dimensional space-time to (F_j+1) -dimensional space-time is represented as [1]:

$$E_{F_j+1} = E_{F_m+1} \cdot \Theta \cdot \left(\frac{U_{F_j+1}}{U_{F_m+1}} \right)^2 = E_{F_m+1} \cdot \Theta \cdot \Phi^{2(j-m)} \quad (2)$$

Where $\Phi = 1.618$ and the transition factor (Θ) is [1]:

$$\Theta = \lambda ON_{m \rightarrow j} \cdot e^{2\pi i \cdot \lambda ON_{m \rightarrow j}} = \left[\frac{F_m \cdot F_m!}{F_j \cdot F_j!} \cdot \left(\frac{U_{F_m+1}}{U_{F_j+1}} \right)^{F_j+1} \right] \cdot e^{2\pi i \cdot \left[\frac{F_m \cdot F_m!}{F_j \cdot F_j!} \cdot \left(\frac{U_{F_m+1}}{U_{F_j+1}} \right)^{F_j+1} \right]} \quad (3)$$

If the primitive matter-energy of the Cosmos (two-dimensional space-time) was E_2 , then this was transformed in the next phases as [2]:

$$E_2 = E_3^m + E_3^s = E_4^m + E_4^s = \dots = E_{F_j+1}^m + E_{F_j+1}^s \quad (4)$$

where: $E_{F_j+1}^m$ and $E_{F_j+1}^s$ is the organized matter-energy and non-organized space-energy, respectively in the (F_j+1) -dimensional space-time.

From (1), (2) and (4), the organized matter-energy is calculated as:

$$E_{F_j+1}^m = E_2 \cdot \left(\Phi^{2(j-2)} \cdot \Theta_{2 \rightarrow 3} \cdot \Theta_{3 \rightarrow 4} \cdot \Theta_{4 \rightarrow 6} \dots \cdot \Theta_{F_{j-1}+1 \rightarrow F_j+1} \right) \quad (5)$$

So, the non-organized space-energy by means of (4) and (5) is calculated as:

$$E_{F_j+1}^s = E_2 \cdot \left(1 - \Phi^{2(j-2)} \cdot \Theta_{2 \rightarrow 3} \cdot \Theta_{3 \rightarrow 4} \cdot \Theta_{4 \rightarrow 6} \dots \cdot \Theta_{F_{j-1}+1 \rightarrow F_j+1} \right) \quad (6)$$

For one transition the increase of non-organized space-energy is calculated as:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta E^s &= E_{F_j+1}^s - E_{F_{j-1}+1}^s = E_{F_{j-1}+1}^m - E_{F_j+1}^m = \\ &= E_2 \cdot \Phi^{2(j-2)} \cdot \left(1 - \Phi^2 \cdot \Theta_{F_{j-1}+1 \rightarrow F_j+1} \right) \left(\Theta_{2 \rightarrow 3} \cdot \Theta_{3 \rightarrow 4} \cdot \Theta_{4 \rightarrow 6} \dots \cdot \Theta_{F_{j-2}+1 \rightarrow F_{j-1}+1} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Fig.1 Decrease of organized matter-energy

The increase of non-organized space-energy is equal to decrease of organized matter-energy following the complex Fibonacci spiral (Fig. 1) [2].

So, the transformation mechanism of TT explains and measures the dark matter-energy, namely the non-organized space-energy and entropy of current phase of Cosmos. This transformation mechanism is the energy-loss mechanism that causes light from intergalactic matter to red-shift (tired light).

3 Evolution of Cosmos

Based on TT [1],[2], the evolution of Cosmos is portrayed in Figure 2. As the infinite-dimensional space absorbs organized matter-energy, hidden space-dimensions are brought out.

Fig. 2. Evolutionary phases of Cosmos

The non-organized space-energy, namely the dark matter-energy is calculated as follows [1]:

$$\left. \begin{array}{l} U_1 = 0.14591029344 \cdot c \\ U_{2A} = 0.236 \cdot c \\ U_2 = 0.382 \cdot c \\ U_3 = 0.618 \cdot c \\ U_4 = c \\ U_6 = 1.618 \cdot c \end{array} \right\} \xrightarrow{(3)} \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \lambda ON_{1 \rightarrow 2A} = 0 \\ \lambda ON_{2A \rightarrow 2} = 0.381678 \\ \lambda ON_{2 \rightarrow 3} = 0.0590207 \\ \lambda ON_{3 \rightarrow 4} = 0.0324146 \\ \lambda ON_{4 \rightarrow 6} = 0.00167205 \end{array} \right\} \xrightarrow{(5),(6)}$$

$$\left. \begin{array}{l} E_{2A} = E_1 \cdot 0 \text{ where: } E_1 \rightarrow |\infty| \\ E_2 = E_{2A} \cdot (-0.7361452 + i0.6768235) = E_{2A} \cdot 1^{<137.40408^\circ} \\ E_3 = E_2 \cdot (0.144 + i0.0559715) = E_2 \cdot 0.1545117^{<21.247452^\circ} = E_{2A} \cdot 0.1545117^{<158.65153^\circ} \\ \Rightarrow \text{dark matter-energy} = 1 - 0.1545117 \cdot \cos(21.247452^\circ) = 85.599\% \\ E_4 = E_3 \cdot (0.0831049 + i0.0171637) = E_3 \cdot 0.0848589^{<11.669256^\circ} = E_2 \cdot 0.0131116^{<32.916708^\circ} \\ = E_{2A} \cdot 0.0131116^{<170.32079^\circ} \\ \Rightarrow \text{dark matter-energy} = 1 - 0.0131116 \cdot \cos(32.916708^\circ) = 98.899\% \\ E_6 = E_4 \cdot 0.00437729^{<0.6019392^\circ} = E_2 \cdot 0.0000573934^{<33.518647^\circ} = E_{2A} \cdot 0.0000573934^{<170.92273^\circ} \\ \Rightarrow \text{dark matter-energy} = 1 - 0.0000573934 \cdot \cos(33.518647^\circ) = 99.995\% \\ \dots\dots\dots \\ E_n \square E_{2A} \cdot \alpha_n^{<g_n^\circ} \text{ where: } n \rightarrow \infty, a_n \rightarrow 0^+, g_n \rightarrow 180^- \\ \Rightarrow \text{dark matter-energy} \rightarrow 100\% \end{array} \right\} (8)$$

Explanation: Time exists due to hidden space-dimensions [1]. So, “before” the Beginning infinite number of space-dimensions was hidden creating or setting Time (*god Cronus = Time (in Greek) was begat - in accordance of Greek mythology*). In this phase infinite Primitive Energy-Plasma ($E_1 \rightarrow |\infty|$) of Cosmos (= *Ether in accordance of Greek philosopher Heraclitus*) was created.

In the second phase, Time (*god Cronus*) was divided (*god Jupiter or Dias (in Greek) = Divider was begat from god Cronus - in accordance of Greek mythology*) revealing the first space-dimension. In this phase the Primitive Energy-Plasma was converted to Anti-Matter-Energy (E_{2A}) as a big two-dimensional (1-D+Time) string.

In the third phase, the primitive anti-matter-energy was shifted to primitive matter-energy (E_2) (*Gaia = Earth or Matter (in Greek) was created - in accordance of Greek mythology*). This phase can be considered as a Big Bang but in the form of a big two-dimensional (1-D+Time) string.

In the fourth phase, the second space-dimension was being brought out absorbing up to 85.599% of the primitive matter-energy (E_2) resulting in the early 3-D Cosmos (2-D+Time).

In the fifth phase, the third dimension has been brought out absorbing more primitive matter-energy (up to 98.899% of the primitive matter-energy (E_2))

resulting in the 4-D Cosmos (3-D+Time).

In the next phases the entropy of Cosmos will continue to be increased as the primitive matter-energy (E_2) will be endlessly absorbing by the revealed infinite space. Time also will be endlessly quenching.

4 Conclusions

The evolutionary phases of Cosmos based on cosmological model of Transition Theory are depicted. The dark matter-energy, namely the non-organized space-energy in the current and early Cosmos is calculated respectively at 98.899% and 85.599% of the primitive organized matter-energy. Today, experimental measurements estimate the dark matter-energy at 95.4% of the primitive matter-energy while in the early Cosmos at value of 85%. So, the theoretical outcomes of Transition Theory compared to the experimental ones present respectively relative errors of 3.6677% and 0.7047%. Conclusively, the primitive matter-energy and Time will be quenching and Cosmos' entropy will be increased while an infinite number of hidden space-dimensions will be revealed.

References

- [1] J. G. Vlachogiannis, Transition Theory: A novel theory for Universe creation and evolution, *Electronic Journal of Theoretical Physics*, 3 (2004), 22-31.
- [2] J. G. Vlachogiannis, From matter-energy to space, *Electronic Journal of Theoretical Physics*, 4 (2004), 11-15.

Received: May, 2010